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Participation of Women in Decision Making and Proprietorship Primarily in Microfinance Institutions

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ABSTRACT

The present study is based on the participation of female group in choice-making and proprietorship of assets on microfinance institutions (MFIs). The research work based on survey of the involvement of women in choice based and proprietorship of 303 male and female groups (178 members of MFIs and 125 non-members). The research conducted at the city of Berhampur which is popularly known as 'silk city' in South Odisha. A questionnaire was equipped for data collection and tested for consistency. The analysis is done based on taking the incidence measures to assess the participation of women in verdict making and having proprietorship of assets. In order to find out consequences of this reading delegate that woman participants of Microfinance institutions considerably affect additional proprietorship of assets. This is ascertained that microfinance has a significant positive impact on ownership of assets and involvement in choice making.

Keywords: Women empowerment, Decision making, Assets ownership, Women MFIs Members

I. INTRODUCTION

The present study procedures the collision of microfinance on member and member who is not associated with micro-finance institutions. The present study states about that woman, mainly not participated in any type of credit based on microfinance under the principle of entrepreneurship is least concerned in choice making and proprietorship of assets in contrast with microfinance member woman. Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) are operational throughout the world to eradicate poverty and are acknowledged for the successful organizations for deficit improvement and to make powerful the women comprising 75 percent of the deprived inhabitants consisting of female groups. (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2014). The research scholars have also acknowledged numerous female groups and their significant contribution in choice making and proprietorship of assets (Dimova, and Gang, 2016).

The objective of the present research paper is to determine the contact of Microfinance institutions on female groups and to find out their choice

making and proprietorship. The findings of this study obviously fulfil this objective. Around the globe is overflowing by means of many types of indifference among the people; community are consist of classes, races, genders, and ethnicities.

It is usually established that women empowerment absolutely affects economic growth; the subject is to make work opportunity for women. Regrettably, poor women have no or minimum decision-making power in family matters, even though women are necessary to do family circle household tasks and supervise habitat behaviour. The Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) have played an important position in empowerment women, so they become a helpful element of nation and people. They also provide micro-credit to a female group in order to please to the eye their role in the public and get empowerment. Most of the MFIs for providing credit for the better system of female group to set up their ventures and also assisting give necessary right of access of microcredit (Ganle, Afriyie, & Segbefia, 2015). The main hub on women empowerment has increased the rate,

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significance of female groups at social and economic sections. Female groups are also being aware of empowered on their participation in choice making, assisting the self-efficacy and proprietorship of assets (constructs of women empowerment). Most of the women desire is also community workers, but there are limitations to prevent women from achieving their goals. So, the occasion given by microfinance institutions is to rise above this restriction (Adair, Berguiga, Afonso, & Haas, 2014).

Women empowerment considered as a significant position for the economic and social growth of every society. The major difficulty is about the decision regarding empowerment of women, and management as below current and ancient societies have shaped an obvious variation between male and female (Van den Bold, Quisumbing, & Gillespie, 2013).

Regrettably, women are 75% of the deprived population and also have extremely inadequate right to use the amenities, which lead to empowerment. Two of the majority significant aspects of empowerment are contribution in choice making and proprietorship of assets, which give assurance and inspire poor women. Among the MFIs maintain the focal point on women empowerment and give them the opportunities to take part in choice-making and proprietorship by giving necessary micro-credit and by pleasing to the eye their extent as an earning person of the family.

Furthermore, Holvoet (2013) found out that woman empowerment is a sequence of procedures by which their regulation larger than a position contact with direct while giving their opinions. The basic opinion is that it can be controlled in terms of physiological requirements and above their attitude, principles, and perspectives. They also focused on the inferior and the impact of secondary groups, which approved from side to side this development of occurrence of psychological possessions and their philosophy into their own decision (Herath,

Guneratne, and Sanderatne, 2016). However, it may be delightful to manage in all aspects that make compulsory by them. Mefalopulos (2008) have found out that in his book World Bank on empowerment “embellishment of assets and capacity of poor people to participation and concur with control impact on those institutions and agencies which is accountable for distressing their lives”. The requirement of basic necessities includes food, shelter, water, and education required by the poor people in order for improving surroundings in the growing independence. Harassed by women empowerment, which stated that disadvantaged female groups should be optimistic by certain rights to monitor their self-interest on account of deliberation that women are more proficient upto a mark in specific decisions to get better their income principles (Nilakantan, Datta, Sinha, & Datta (2013). Ganle *et. al* (2015) also stated empowerment as a potential from one group to create considered life decisions in the background where this capacity was one time deprived of to her. Husain, Mukherjee, & Dutta (2014) has described empowerment is a potential tool from one individual to another for creating some specific decisions based on the background where her capacity is determined to some extent. The word empowerment also makes one’s choice to live or survive, one’s decision also depends upon either to survive or to get married or not

Choice Making

Women can make manage domestic possession beyond they cannot make the appropriate decision in the outside surroundings on account of they do not desire to take high risk. Usually, microfinance institutions are the worst suffers from high risk and supplementary risk to avoid bigger action. Women do not have to control the assets in making a decision. Nilakantha *et al.* (2013) confirmed women in Eastern India are more empowered on account of microfinance for living in a better environment on their day to day requirement concerning various issues and right to entry as they borrowed money from different

microfinance institutions. Khadar (2014) find out that micro-loans are considered to be useful to improve the way of life, and self-assurance personality based on rules, regulations on account of they are trained from the first day. On the other hand, from the philanthropic point of view, various opportunities, loans, training are being provided for the participation in decision-making process at their residence.

Proprietorship

Women have higher standard age in comparison to men and have a smaller amount of earning and other perks. This feature confronts women with a wider danger of in front of the financial crisis against men. It is well known to all that women have less savings and less possession of assets which make them more powerless. There are different techniques available for the proprietorship of resources to women which also to furnish them less empowerment to formulate concerning decision regarding purchase of assets. (Fonseca *et al.*, 2012). Yadav *et al.*, (2015) found out in advanced countries where identical rights given to male and female in comparison to underdeveloped countries as the same rights are not available to women. For this purpose, most of the microfinance institutions put their hard work have a most important focus on women inhabitants for empowerment and providing prospect in the country.

Intra-household Bargaining authority

It is stated that the belongings and consequences of profits earned from Self Help Groups (SHGs) actions which enable them for choice-making shifts between income earned from their saving and expenditure or types of payments.

Better economic possessions

Enhanced economic possessions has an optimistic contact on expenditure influence and their suggestion make to every day buying, increases in individual and health everyday

expenditure such as contraceptives or medicine (Adair *et al.* 2014).

Inspiration

It has been observed that the sequence of empowerment is not merely present the basis of encouragement towards the women, but further encourages a good number of significant instances for the period to come. This indication comes after they are appearing by all persons who will acquire well-informed and progressive (Bhattacharya, 2014).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Modi, Patel, & Patel (2014) discussed the consequence of microfinance services to sanction the women of rural areas and also the factors empowering the women. Further, it also was conducted in North of Gujarat area of India. The researchers originate that four factors that are, independence of choices in existence, come up to towards growth of children, an arrangement of women in humanity, and upgradation of socio-economic position were important in conditions of their contact on women empowerment. Nilakantan, Datta, Sinha, & Datta (2013) worked on the strength of mind based on the vital force of microfinance on the basis of the empowerment of women. Owing to the environment of study, they only incorporated women borrows. The four aspects they are considered, such as supervision of microenterprise, the authority on production matters including credit and expenditure, and pressure on the issues of children. They had assorted consequences, the only erratic by which establish importantly was pressure on matters associated with children in their relatives. Nasir & Farooqi (2016) calculated the consequence of microfinance on the enchanting element of women in choice making. They examined to observe the probable of microfinance in achieving the goal of empowering women. The authors measured the socioeconomic factors of women empowerment in the Aligarh district of India. And

they found there is an important control of microfinance on both social and economic aspects of women's life. Kato & Kratzer (2013) conducted a study on women empowerment in Tanzania. Their top of research was to think high concentration rates of microfinance in the country, which has a harmful contact on women. This learning had both quantitative and qualitative aspects. They found that even with elevated interest rates microcredit brings recovered change in the lives of women and hence empowers them. The test consists of about 500 women who were members and non-members that are borrowers and non-borrowers of microfinance. They create that member women are improved empowered in conditions of proceeds, investments, decision making, and self-esteem. Yadav & Verma (2015) studied women empowerment within the family circle capital by using sample data from countries like India, Brazil, South Africa, China, and the UK. They initiate that control of women on household income increases with microfinance. They also further stated that borrowers of microfinance have advanced level of assurance than the additional women.

Kapila, Singla, & Gupta (2016) carried out on research the position of microfinance from side to side based on arrangement on women empowerment role played by the Self Help Groups in India. They took the sample data from the state of Punjab which consists of 106 leaders and 318 member of these groups participated in the research. The study found that it showed that there was a important improvement in the profits of members and therefore there was a optimistic contact on family decision making. They establish that women borrowers of better amounts of micro credit were more empowered. Pakkanna, Arsyad and Suryantoro (2015) make a study on married women who use microfinance and to decide on the impact on their lives. They used a descriptive analysis in their research. They found that result of women empowerment as important and variables on the basis of the size of loan,

expenditure, living cost, access to teaching and others have no significant dissimilarity on microfinance. They also found that microfinance models with minimum capital necessity, having more flexibility, permanent and customer paying attention are more successful in terms of women empowerment.

Garikipati (2013) reviewed to settle the optimistic and pessimistic possessions of micro credit of empowerment of women in his research. She attempted that studies to be focused on access to loans showed positive effects, whereas studies connected to use of it showed a negative effect. She also used sample data of about 400 women in the rural areas of India and also found that bearing in mind empowerment just in conditions of outcomes is deceptive. She further suggested that focused be supposed to be on the employ of credit and reimbursement processes. Dash, Prasad, & Koshy (2016) considered the collision of microfinance on different factors of empowerment of women, namely, political, socioeconomic, savings, and income. The study was also done in India in the State of Kerala on a sample of 225 women. The consequences showed an important impact on the revenue and savings of microfinance borrowers.

Herath, Guneratne, & Sanderatne (2015) studied how socio-economic limitation and scarcity of women can be concentrated using microfinance, chiefly through collection lending. They find out the variables to review empowerment in expressions of right of entry to possessions, decision making, assurance, and standing in humanity. The researchers also used Empowerment guide to review the force on women. They had also used Women Empowerment Indices (WEIs) to find out the various effect of microfinance.

Hossain (2015) had find out on microfinance and women empowerment in Bangladesh mentioned various development actions carried out by microfinance institutions for the women of the country. He adopted alternate variables for

empowerment he establishes that the contact of microfinance was important. Chant (2016) raised on motivating position in his exploration about provided that acclaim to women, empowering them and sinking poverty. He also further stated that the feminization of poverty also has some compensation. This study is about the three interventions for poor women by Nike Foundation including microfinance, cash transfers, and investing in Girls. The results were found significant.

The literature reviewed concerning women empowerment find out that usually microfinance considerably affects women empowerment. Different detailed areas of empowerment as discussed by various researchers, showed varied results. Therefore this investigates with high opinion to two explicit areas of empowerment that is, decision making and ownership in Indian point of view is fairly important.

III. PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES IN MICRO FINANCE

Most of the researchers have decorated that persistent poverty and underdevelopment among the women prevailed across India since independence. Despite, a number of methods taken by the Government, the situation is not very acceptable on account of accessible evils in the financial sector and society. The major problems and challenges as painted by the various studies, are as under:

- Not have of adequate knowledge to promote for entering into business;
- Insufficient knowledge of office work and accounting
- Service of a lot of workers that increases distribution of profits, group lending;
- Wealth shortage and high-interest rates;
- Inventory and price increases in accounting;

- Errors in praise policies;
- Monetary inclusion in the tribal and most backward rural areas;
- Conflicts for the breakup of the Groups; and
- Internal family problems, established household tasks of the women.

Way forward

- Awareness campaign for the women about their rights, responsibilities, etc.;
- Attaining full women literacy to strengthen the awareness campaign;
- Extension of women oriented training/ skill for employment and earning;
- Growth of a well-built mutual reproduction among banks, NGOs, MFIs and Women's organizations to work out most excellent practices and
- Framing policies for financial sustainability of poor women for creating community owned institutions;
- Efficiently completion of the gender strategies in micro finance in a broad way for rising providing necessary credit facilities and self-help groups in a strategic thinking for promoting women empowerment. (Mayoux, L.1998a)

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this paper data preferred from Microfinance institutions carried out in the course of a self-administered questionnaire, the subject is useful quantitative come up to on principal data collected during random sample method in the year 2020. In order to measure various statistical tools are used from Kato *et al.* (2013). The inhabitant's covers in this research paper cover deprived women by which micro-credit from different microfinance organizations from various locations of India.

Table-1 : Proprietorship of Assets

Assets in number	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
1	16	9.0	48	38.4
2	34	19.1	35	28.0
3	57	32.0	27	21.6
4	44	24.7	15	12.0
5	17	9.6		
6	7	3.9		
7	2	1.1		
8	1	0.6		
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The comparative difference among the proprietorship of assets between women members of micro-finance institutions and women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions shown in Table-1. Most of the women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions having one or two assets in their proprietorship. It has been suggested that comparison is made to find out most of the women members of Microfinance institutions. It depends on the empowerment of women with micro-entrepreneurial works funded by micro-finance institutions.

Table-2: Purchase of Grocery items

Decision taken by women members	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	100	56.2	16.8	
Spouse	33	18.5	25	20.0
Self + Spouse only	40	22.5	28	22.4
Someone else	4	2.2	28	22.4
Jointly with someone else	1	0.6	23	18.4
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 points out involvement of women from two samples in the purchase of grocery items concerning different products as well as women members of microfinance institutions. As they have additional capacity for purchase of grocery items the grocery items.

Table-3: Purchase of cloth items

Particulars on decision makers	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	105	59	19	15
Spouse	25	14	20	16
Self + Spouse only	31	17	30	24
Someone else	09	06	34	27
Jointly with someone else	08	04	22	18
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 shows the purchase of cloth items undertaken through Microfinance institutions members consisting of both women and non-member women also presents an enormous distinction of participation as Women members of micro-finance institutions have much superior percentage of decision-making power than the Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions.

Table-4 : Self Items decision

Particulars on decision makers	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	130	73.0	29	23.2
Spouse	22	12.4	31	24.8
Self + Spouse only	18	10.1	35	28.0
Someone else	5	2.8	19	15.2
Jointly with someone else	3	1.7	11	8.8
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 4 represents the decision of purchasing of self-items and it points out a significant contribution on the influence of decision making surrounded by the Women members of Microfinance institutions in comparison to women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions. With regards to decision making on women members in not related to micro-finance institutions on account by their spouse or by Self and spouse on the basis of jointly.

Table-5: Decision by the women members on purchasing of Pots-Pans

Decision makers women	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	94	52	22	17.6
Spouse	22	12	21	16.8
Self + Spouse only	41	24	31	24.8
Someone else	09	5	26	20.8
Jointly with someone else	12	7	25	20.0
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 presents in the various approach adopted with regard to the decision regarding the details of the purchase on pots and pans. It is observed that majority of taken by women members of micro-finance institutions itself in comparison to a low percentage represents women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions. It is observed that 7 has suggested to find out the dissimilarity on consequences in distinction of earlier tables and describes an elevated choice making of spouse in conditions of female group members of micro-finance institutions.

Table 6: Decision on Repairing of House

Particulars on various decision	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	60	33.7	23	18.4
Spouse	75	42.1	24	19.2
Self + Spouse only	32	18.0	19	15.2
Someone else	10	5.6	31	24.8
Jointly with someone else	1	0.6	28	22.4
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table-6 presents on house repairing decisions are taken by majority of members for Microfinance institutions in a smaller amount in comparison to involvement of non-member for their decision-making.

Table-7: Land purchase Decisions

Particulars on decision makers	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	61	34.3	27	21.6
Spouse	71	39.9	19	15.2
Self + Spouse only	33	18.5	26	20.8
Someone else	12	6.7	30	24.0
Jointly with someone else	1	0.6	23	18.4
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

It is evident from Table 7 that participation of Microfinance institutions members have significantly soared in decision making in relationship to non-member women, but they have a fewer contribution in decision making than their partner.

Table-8: Household Decisions

Particulars on decision makers	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	38	21.3	22	17.6
Spouse	61	34.3	25	20.0
Self + Spouse only	62	34.8	23	18.4
Someone else	15	8.4	24	19.2
Jointly with someone else	2	1.1	31	24.8
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The decision regarding building the house is also very significant and taking part of Microfinance institutions member women is superior to the non-member women but the difference is not very towering. If the two sections combined here for further clarification which is Self and jointly Self and spouse, then the percentage of member women is 56.1 and non-members are having 36 percent participation and it shows a significant difference in two samples.

Table 9: Purchase decisions of various equipment

Particulars on decision makers	Women members of micro-finance institutions		Women members in not associated with micro-finance institutions	
	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
Self	68	38.2	27	21.6
Spouse	38	21.3	37	29.6
Self + Spouse only	66	37.1	13	10.4
Someone else	3	1.7	27	21.6
Jointly with someone else	3	1.7	21	16.8
Total	178	100.0	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 9 shows that participation of Microfinance Institutions member women in decision making is higher than the non-member women and it

shows that credit given by Microfinance Institutions for micro-entrepreneurship among women enhances their empowerment as they are more indulged in the decision-making process. The study further shows that microfinance plays a crucial role in the participation of women in decision making and ownership. A revision shows the related results as shown by De Brauw *et al.*, (2014), Nilakantan *et al.*, (2013), Bhaumik *et al.*, (2016), Kato & Kratzer, (2013) concerning the impact of microfinance on decision making power of women in intra-household matters but this study, in contrast, explore the kind of decision making women involved like equipment purchase decision, house build decision, land purchase decision etc., it identifies the worth of decision in which women involved. While talking about proprietorship of assets by women also shows the impact of microfinance similar to many studies (Dash *et al.*, 2016; Fonseca *et al.*, 2012; Kato & Kratzer, 2013; Yadav and Verma, 2015).

V. MAJOR FINDINGS

The impact of microfinance on female participation in the decision-making and ownership process of these micro-finance institutions (MFIs) in India based on the responses collected from the distribution of primary questionnaire. The results suggest that women members of MFIs have considerably higher involvement in decision making and have more ownership of assets. Contribution of women in economic activities is particularly significant to attain inclusive growth. To accelerate the process of completeness, a number of fiscal inclusion actions have already been done through a growing number of banks and MFIs and noteworthy economic and social empowerment of women through SHGs have been pictured. Nevertheless, a group desires to be recognized in a widespread measurement to decrease the breach between rich and poor. In so far as microfinance on the involvement of women in decision making and ownership women is concerned, it is a long-term feature and consistent

hard work need to be unexpectedly drifted out from each angle of the society. Government's effort from side to side crafty and implementing various policies for generating and providing financial supports may be well behind attaining the millennium growth goals for microfinance in decision making for a strong willingness, efforts and utilization power is developed by the women and their families. The dream of eradicating poverty and hunger from women/ society can only be achieved when the beneficiaries can excavate out the multiplier effect of the funds (cash or kind) and services supported. The Government/ financial institutions have the innovative steps taken through the SHGs must be welcomed and be extended to many poor women for their empowerment to build a new, healthy and violence-free women empowered and developed. This can fulfil the aim of inclusive growth.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present study is focusing on the role of women as empowered population and its optimistic outcomes on their existence excellence

and for the public as a whole. The study also further recommends that women's entrepreneurial can be improved through facilitations like microfinance institutes. The functions of Microfinance Institutions in establishing and empowering women is of a prominent role in India for a few important reasons. Moreover, the country is a rising one with the help of female members affecting the round of life.

The outcome also stated that women from Microfinance institutions have complementary choice-making capability and possessions ownership through managerial work. The findings also recommend that those women belong to dynamically concerned in their income for their families as a whole a lot of outcomes for improvement of self-efficacy. It also suggests financial support for the prospective improvement on the economic fibre of not only their homes but also the nation jointly. At last more recommendations made for the more microfinance institutions on the elastic and easy sufficient for women.

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